

**DISCURS POLIMORF ÎN CORESPONDENȚA LUI VASILE VASILACHE /
POLYMORPHOUS DISCOURSE IN THE CORRESPONDENCE
OF VASILE VASILACHE**

Maria ABRAMCIUC, Associate Professor,
Researcher-Coordinator, PhD
(The “Bogdan Petriceicu-Hasdeu” Institute
of Romanian Philology, Moldova State University)
margacurtescu@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0186-0224>

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Our research deals with the specific aspects of epistolary discourse organization in the love correspondence of the writer Vasile Vasilache. These letters, composite constructions *par excellence* in which the dominant discourse is erotic, are addressed to the young Marianna Lomako and are characterized by a heterogeneous thematic structure and enunciative polyphony. The polymorphism of the discourse is a defining feature of these letters, which are shaped both by sentiment and a narrative impulse. Within the epistolary space, the speaker inserts details about his intimate emotions, confessions about his creative activities, meditations, essayistic sequences, mini-reviews of literary works, short stories, journal entries, paraphrases, and more - all of which reveal the writer’s deliberate application of rhetorical strategies.